

Impact of Eco-Friendly Household Products on Customers

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Abstract:- In today's world, the public has begun to realize the importance of sustainable development and look out for products that cause less minimum harm to the living environment. Therefore, companies have adopted several green marketing strategies to meet the demands of the public. Sustainable products are those products that provide environmental, social and economic benefits while protecting public health and environment over their whole life cycle, from the extraction of raw materials until the final disposal. Many of the world's most valuable and successful companies are pursuing green marketing initiatives.

While green marketing can be more expensive than traditional marketing messages and practices, but it can also be profitable due to increasing demand. This study focuses on the production of sustainable household items and products used on an everyday basis. The research aims to understand the consumer's accessibility to such products and the impact it has on the buying behaviour.

The study aims to understand the level of awareness of consumers and the direct relationship in the consumption of the products, which segment of the society is more aware, and the resources available to them to understand the ways in which these products can be marketed and promoted. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The questionnaire is designed to obtain the consumers attitudes and perception regarding eco-friendly household products.

This paper finds that most consumers aren't unaware of the products available to them and do have a desire to purchase eco-friendly and sustainable products. However, majority of them find the price of the products to be expensive. They also hold the belief that the brands claiming to be eco friendly are not very reliable.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, the consumers are more aware of the choices they make and how their decisions affect the people around them in their living environment. Everyone desires to uphold a certain image against their name as an individual and does not want to be labelled as someone whose minor choices lead to the contribution of something negative. This holds the same for the consumption of products that cause harm to the

environment. Thus, today's public opt for the consumption in sustainable and "green" products.

Sustainable products are those products that are sustainable, natural, and eco-friendly. This means that the product will not only protect our environment for future generations but also helps us live better by making healthier decisions. Sustainable products are sustainable in both their use of resources as well as their production methods and substances used during manufacturing.

However, there are several factors hindering customers from purchasing said eco-friendly products. These products are sometimes not easy to access and usually fall on the expensive margin. Household products are naturally consumed on a daily basis and the public switching to an eco-friendly alternative would show a great impact as the frequency in its purchase would be comparatively higher when compared to other sustainable products.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dipti Shankar Barge (Eco -friendly products attitude toward pricing, 2015) stated that users of eco-friendly products exhibit favourable attitude in the pricing of sustainable products. they show readiness in buying those items which are more expensive but cause less harm to the environment.

Dyah (eco- friendly product design, 2021) stated that eco-friendly literature mostly comprises of the behaviour of green customers. It is mostly studied in countries who have high income levels. According to their study an individuals income had a lot of impact on whether or not they purchased sustainable products.

Graduateway identified various barriers such as availability, affordability, convenience, product performance, conflicting priorities and force of habit which keep consumers from purchasing the sustainable products. It was also to be noted that neither the customers nor the manufacturers state any environmental positives on the packaging of a product.

P. Anitha in the paper on an empirical Study on green products and green marketing (December 2020) interpreted that the vital problems concerning the environment and the depletion of natural resources forced the society to focus on the sustainable products. It was also understood that there is

no significant correlation between an individual and their gender, occupation and level of awareness they had about the sustainable products.

➤ *Objectives*

- To measure consumer satisfaction in consumption of eco-friendly products.
- To study the effects of government environment policies on buying behaviour.
- To identify ways to make the products accessible to customers.
- To compare the expenses incurred in the purchase of eco-friendly and non-eco-friendly products.
- To identify the customers level of awareness on eco-friendly products.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ *Population*

The population of this study are consumers in general irrespective of whether they purchase sustainable products or if they are exposed to them

➤ *Sample*

The sample size for this study is 100

➤ *Data Collection Method*

Data for this research has been collected with the help of both primary as well as secondary sources.

• *Primary Data*

Primary data was collected from the consumers of different age groups with the help Google Forms questionnaire

• *Secondary Data*

Secondary data was collected from research articles, publications, journals, business magazines and newspapers.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: Demographics

Particulars	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	33	33%
	Female	62	62%
	Prefer not to say	4	4%
	Other	1	1%
Age	Under 18	9	9%
	18-30	73	73%
	31-50	17	17
	Above 50	1	1
Occupation	Student	61	61
	Employed	39	39
Income	Above 60000	40	40
	Below 60000	33	33
	Nil	27	27

Table 2 : Perceptions on sustainable products

Particulars	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
What are the most important features you look for while purchasing a product	Price	30	30
	Quality	59	59
	Availability	4	4
	Impact on environment	7	7
Do you buy eco-friendly household products	Yes	35	35
	No	7	7
	Sometimes	58	58
	Heath	30	30
Reasons for purchase	Environment	49	49
	Quality	17	17
	Other	4	4
	Household	27	27
Type of Products	Personal Care	43	43

Reasons preventing purchase	Gifts	17	17
	Other	5	5
	Do not purchase	8	8
	Price	42	42
	Quality	17	17
	Availability	29	29
	Lack of interest	12	

I recommend Eco friendly products to friends and family	Strongly agree	16	16
	Agree	36	36
	Neutral	33	33
	Disagree	12	12
	Strongly Disagree	3	3
I don't find the need to use products that are eco-friendly and sustainable	Strongly agree	1	1
	Agree	14	14
	Neutral	38	38
	Disagree	30	30
	Strongly Disagree	8	8
I am willing to pay a premium price for an eco-friendly product	Strongly agree	4	4
	Agree	22	22
	Neutral	35	35
	Disagree	31	31
	Strongly Disagree	8	8
Environment friendly products are just a trend	Strongly agree	11	11
	Agree	24	24
	Neutral	30	30
	Disagree	29	29
	Strongly Disagree	6	6

Table 3: Rating on aspects of the products

Particulars	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Accessibility	Good	37	37
	Average	57	57
	Bad	6	6
Price	Good	21	21
	Average	54	54
	Bad	25	25
Reliability	Good	40	40
	Average	53	53
	Bad	7	7
Advertising	Good	46	46
	Average	37	37
	Bad	17	17

V. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

The general consumers are well aware of the option of choosing the sustainable products. They don't necessarily find availability to be an issue even if they are unsure of a products location as they are easily available on online platforms.

Household products are more likely to be purchased by consumers when compared to other products second to products used for hygiene and personal care. This backs the previous finding on the preference of quality to price.

Consumers prefer quality and price when it comes to making purchasing decisions. Environmental effects of the product purchased is not a primary factor. There was no negative feedback given on the quality of the sustainable products. It is just the price that majorly prevents the purchase of sustainable products.

Thus, people belonging to the higher income groups purchased said products on a more regular basis than the people belonging to lower income groups or those who are not in employment.

It was found that consumers rated the advertising and marketability aspect of sustainable products higher when compared to its other features like quality, price and availability. As mentioned in several researches, price is yet again a feature with the least rating.

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